

Towards Inclusive Democracy: Reforming Nepal's Electoral System for Fair Representation and Governance

Govinda Prasad Guragain

*Associate Professor, Tribhuvan University, Padmakanya Multiple Campus,
Department of Political Science, Bagbazar, Kathmandu, Nepal*

Saroj Pokharel

*Lecturer, Tribhuvan University, Active Academy College,
Department of Sociology, Basundhara, Kathmandu, Nepal*

Bhawani Shankar Adhikari, Ph.D

*Associate Professor, Nepal Sanskrit University, Department of English,
Balmiki Campus, Exhibition Road, Kathmandu, Nepal*

Suggested Citation

Guragain, G.P., Pokharel, S., & Adhikari, B.S. (2024). Towards Inclusive Democracy: Reforming Nepal's Electoral System for Fair Representation and Governance. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 66-77. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).07](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).07)

Abstract:

The purpose of this research paper is to examine various electoral systems used worldwide and to determine the most suitable electoral system for Nepal as it transitions into a federal system. It aims to explore inclusive democracy and the electoral practices observed in contemporary politics and Constituent Assembly (CA) polls. The discussion centers on the challenges faced in Nepal's political landscape, particularly focusing on the First-Past-The-Post (FPTP) and List Proportional Representation (List PR) systems utilized in the CA elections of 2008 and 2013. The paper evaluates the merits and drawbacks of different electoral systems implemented globally,

providing insights into selecting an appropriate system for Nepal. It also analyzes the outcomes of the 2008 CA elections and proposes reforms for enhancing the fairness and inclusivity of the FPTP and List PR systems, or potentially adopting a Parallel Mixed System or another electoral framework that better aligns with Nepal's context and aspirations for proportional representation.

Keywords: *Constituent Assembly, drawback, elections, Proportional Representation, reform.*

Introduction

Studying electoral systems presents a complex challenge, as no single system universally proves to be ideal for every country. Nonetheless, Baral (2009) has argued about the local leadership and governance in Nepal and it is clarified that the consensus remains that elected governance outshines non-elected forms. Therefore, Dahal (2009) has pleaded about the electoral system and inclusive democracy in Nepal and it has been

explained that the intricacies of elections and their systems warrant thorough discussion, given that elections serve as the cornerstone of representative democracies. Mishra (2008) has explained about the election system about the past experience and the future destination and he has mapped out about the election system that elections are widely recognized as the democratic means through which the people select their representatives based on popular will.

According to Nohlen, an electoral system defines the framework within which voters express their political preferences and through which votes are translated into parliamentary seats in legislative elections, forming the basis for executive formation. The electoral system significantly shapes various aspects of the political system where electoral practices are prevalent. As Nohlen asserts, it influences factors such as voting behavior and election outcomes, defining the character and functioning of political representation and party systems within a specific political and electoral framework. Hence, the electoral system plays a pivotal role in shaping political preferences and facilitating the transfer of power within any political system.

Statement of the Problem

Inclusive democracy has become one of the modern agendas of the world today. The electoral system has to be reformed and addressed the voice of the marginalized groups and the representation of all the suppressed and oppressed as well as the of those out of the mainstream of the nation's politics have to be incorporated through the electoral system in Nepal. Hence, the research has attempted to reveal the answers of the following research questions.

A) what are the electoral systems to be adopted for fair representation and governance in Nepal?

B) How can it become possible to include all the marginalized groups of the nation through electoral system in the country?

The Objective of the Research

This paper aims to thoroughly examine various aspects of electoral systems and advocate for the most suitable system for Nepal, as the country prepares for elections at the presidential, central, state, and local levels. The study begins by analyzing theoretical and conceptual aspects of electoral systems practiced across different countries worldwide. It also evaluates the merits and drawbacks of these systems, aiming to identify achievements and determine the optimal electoral system for Nepal. This decision is

informed by discussions on existing challenges, examining Nepal's unique circumstances such as its diverse society where administrative divisions intersect with various ethnic groups and communities.

Historically, Nepal initially adopted the First-Past-The-Post System (FPTP) since the introduction of its electoral system. However, the country also implemented the Proportional Representation (PR) system during the Constituent Assembly elections held on 28th Chaitra 2064 (April 10, 2008 AD) and 4th Manghir 2070 (November 20, 2013 AD).

Now, there are some questions to be discussed

a) What electoral system should be implemented for the different levels of elections in a federal system?

b) Isn't it crucial to discuss the challenges and issues encountered with both the FPTP and PR systems during the CA elections?

c) Were the CA elections held on 28 Chaitra 2064 (April 10, 2008 AD) and 4 Manghir 2070 (November 20, 2013 AD) conducted in a inclusive, impartial, free, and fair manner?

d) What type of electoral system do political parties prefer?

e) What electoral system would be most effective for a country like Nepal to ensure fair representation of all diverse groups from the local to the central levels?

The Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of the research are to answer the research questions and its goal is:

A) To explore what the electoral systems to be adopted for fair representation and governance in Nepal.

B) To investigate how can it become possible to include all the marginalized groups of the nation through electoral system in the country

The Research Methodology

The research has historical and analytical method in exploring the facts of improving the electoral system in including the voices of the marginalized and other backwards groups. The research has adopted both a descriptive and analytical methodology, drawing on secondary sources obtained from diverse channels. These sources encompass library resources, online materials, published works such as newspapers, books, magazines, and archived documents, which focus on themes of inclusion, policy formulation, and political representation. Statistical data and historical evidence are derived from reputable sources to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the information. Additionally, authoritative websites and external

links are consulted to explore established theories and concepts.

Furthermore, the study integrates contemporary developments in the current political environment, engaging in critical analysis and constructive discourse. The researcher's personal insights and viewpoints enrich the study's findings, contributing to a deeper and comprehensive understanding of the subject matter.

Description

There exist multiple electoral systems in use across countries globally, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. The following chart illustrates the diversity of electoral systems worldwide.

Figure 1. The Electoral Systems and Their Impacts

Source: Andrew Reynolds, Ben Reilly, and Andrew Ellis: *The Systems and Their Consequences / Case Study of Six Countries* / Nohlen, Dieter, and Kumar Sushil: *Elections and Electoral Systems*

Electoral Systems Practiced in the World

The global electoral system has got its various forms and they have become useful for all the nations in the world. Different nations have adopted different forms of the electoral system as the need of their nations and it has to do as the requirement of the different countries. Among them the followings are the different types of the electoral systems adopted in the world.

Plurality/Majority system

The principle of the Plurality/Majority system is straightforward: following the casting and counting of votes, the candidate or party receiving the highest number of votes is declared the winner. Robert (1999) has discussed about the integration and disintegration regarding the electoral system and has clarified that this system is extensively implemented in practice across many regions. There are five distinct variations of this system that can be identified.

a) FPTP (First-Past-The-Post System):

This system awards victory to the candidate or party with the highest number of votes after all votes are counted.

b) AV (Alternative Vote):

Also known as instant-runoff voting, this system allows voters to rank candidates in order of preference. If no candidate receives a majority in the first round, the candidate with the fewest votes is eliminated, and their votes are redistributed according to voters' second preferences. This process continues until a candidate achieves a majority.

c) BV (Block Vote):

In the Block Vote system, voters have as many votes as there are seats to be filled. They can allocate these votes among candidates freely, and the candidates with the highest individual vote totals are elected.

d) PBV (Party Block Vote):

This variation of the Block Vote system allows voters to cast their vote for a party rather than

individual candidates. Parties are allocated seats in proportion to their share of the vote.

e) TRS (Two Round System):

In the Two Round System, a candidate must secure an absolute majority (more than 50% of the votes) to win in the first round. If no candidate achieves this, a second round of voting is held between the top two candidates from the first round, and the candidate with the most votes in the second round is declared the winner.

a) First-Past-The-Post System

The First-Past-The-Post System (FPTP) is the most straightforward version of the Plurality/Majority electoral system, characterized by single-member districts and voter focus on individual candidates. Under this system, the candidate who receives more votes than any other contender wins the seat, even if the margin of victory is minimal, sometimes just one or two votes. Approximately 22% of countries worldwide employ the FPTP System, including nations like the UK, Canada, India, Malaysia, and Bangladesh.

The merits of FPTP system:

- Provides a straightforward decision for voters.
 - Enables voters to select both political parties and individual candidates.
 - Prevents extremist parties from gaining legislative representation.
 - Facilitates the formation of single-party governments.
 - Enhances geographical accountability by linking constituencies directly to the legislature.
- The demerits of FPTP system:
- Encourages the formation of political parties organized around clan or ethnicity.
 - Limits fair representation for smaller political parties.
 - Results in a significant number of wasted votes.

- Excludes representation for common minorities.
- Leads to vote splitting issues.

b) Alternative Vote System

The Alternative Vote System is a preferential form of the Plurality/Majority system utilized in single-member districts. Andrew and Andrew have talked about the system and their result of the election system and it has become obvious that voters rank candidates in order of preference using numbers on the ballot. A candidate who secures an outright majority of valid first preference votes is declared the winner. If no candidate reaches this majority, the least successful candidates are eliminated, and their votes are redistributed based on the next preference marked on the ballots. This process continues until one candidate achieves an absolute majority. Countries that employ this system include Australia, Papua New Guinea, Fiji, and it is also used in presidential elections in Ireland.

The merits of AV system:

- Supports a candidate who may be unlikely to win, offering them backing.
 - Allows votes to be transferred, enabling multiple candidates to accumulate votes advantageously.
 - Focuses on selecting candidates based on second preferences rather than party affiliations.
 - Combines various yet interconnected interests to secure representation.
 - Encourages cooperative and accommodating politics by providing substantial incentives.
- The demerits of AV system:
- Demands a basic level of literacy and numeracy skills.
 - Shows limitations in effectiveness when used in larger districts with multiple members.

- Frequently yields outcomes that are not proportionate when compared to systems like PR or FPTP.

- The promotion of centrist results heavily relies on the underlying social and demographic factors.

c) Block Vote System

The block vote system, a type of Plurality/Majority system applied in multi-member districts, grants voters a number of votes equal to the seats available in their district. Werner (1991) has discussed about the society and the electoral system as well as the electoral system by the inclusiveness of the majority of the people and it has become clear that voters typically have the freedom to allocate their votes among individual candidates rather than party affiliations, using all or some of their allotted votes as they choose. The candidate receiving the highest total votes secure the seats. Countries employing this system include Kuwait, Laos, Lebanon, Tonga, Tuvalu, among others.

The merits of BV system:

- Preserving the voter's option to choose individual candidates
- Supporting the use of moderately sized geographical districts.
- Enhancing the influence of political parties compared to the FPTP system.
- Empowering parties that exhibit greater coherence and organizational capability.

The demerits of BV system:

- Lead to unexpected and sometimes undesirable effects on election results.
- Enable a single party to achieve dominance.
- Allow a party to secure more seats with a lower percentage of the total votes.
- Pose significant challenges for the efficient operation of a parliamentary system.

d) Party Block Vote System

The party block vote system is a Plurality/Majority system applied in multi-member districts, where voters cast a unified party vote instead of selecting individual candidates. Election Commission Report (2064) has pointed out about the system of making the constitution and it has shown the role of the political parties and identified that the party receiving the most votes secures all seats in the electoral districts, without needing to achieve an absolute majority of votes. This electoral method was predominantly observed in four countries by 2004: Cameroon, Chad, Djibouti, and Singapore.

The means of PBV system:

- Encourages strong parties
- Ensures balanced ethnic representation.
- Allows parties to put up mixed slates of candidates for minority representation.
- Enables parties to present ethnically diverse lists of candidates for elections.
- The demerits of PBV system:
 - Can lead to outcomes that are significantly disproportionate.
 - One party often secures the vast majority of seats.
 - Occasionally results in situations where there is no opposition present.

Two Round System

The Two Round system is a Plurality/Majority electoral method where a second election round occurs if no candidate or party reaches a specified threshold of votes, typically an absolute majority (50%) in the initial round. Susil Kumar has talked about the election and electoral system and clarified that in the second round, which may involve more than two candidates, only those at the top in the first round can compete, and the candidate with the highest votes in the second round wins the seat. This system is utilized in countries such as Congo, Gabon, Mali, Haiti, Iran, Georgia, Egypt, and others.

The merits of this system:

- Provides voters with an opportunity for a second vote to support their preferred candidates.
- Promotes the consolidation of diverse interests around winning candidates.
- Reduces the issue of vote splitting.
- Allows voters to make a completely new choice in the second round if they wish to do so.

The demerits of this system:

- Imposes significant demands on the electoral management.
- Shares many of the drawbacks associated with the FPTP system.
- Has implications for societies with deep divisions.
- Might lead the opposition to refrain from participating in the second round.

Semi Proportional Representation

Semi Proportional Representation combines elements of both proportional representation and plurality/majority systems. This electoral system offers voters increased options and alternatives, allowing them to vote based on parties and enhancing inclusivity compared to the FPTP system.

There are two types of this system:

- a) Parallel Mixed System
- b) SNTV (Single Non-Transferable Vote)

These two variations include:

- a) Parallel Mixed System
- b) SNTV (Single Non-Transferable Vote)

Parallel Mixed System

The Parallel Mixed System incorporates both proportional representation (PR) and plurality/majority components. However, unlike other systems, the PR component in this system does not offset any disproportionality within the plurality/majority districts. Lok Raj(1998) has discussed about the democratization and crisis

of governance in Nepal and has revealed that it operates as a dual system where voters' preferences determine representatives through both PR and plurality/majority mechanisms simultaneously. This approach is employed in countries such as Armenia, Pakistan, South Korea, Japan, Seychelles, Russia, and Senegal.

The merits of Parallel system: Typically produces outcomes that fall between those of purely parallel/majority and purely PR systems.

Leads to less fragmentation of the party system compared to a pure PR system.

Allows small minority parties to potentially achieve more seats through proportional allocation.

The demerits of Parallel system:

Creates two categories of representatives. It does not ensure complete proportionality, potentially excluding some parties from representation. It is relatively intricate and may cause confusion among voters regarding the system's structure and functioning.

b) Single Non-Transferable Vote system

The Single Non-Transferable Vote (SNTV) system enables voters to cast one vote in multi-member districts. Candidates with the highest vote counts win seats, with voters selecting individual candidates rather than parties, even though multiple seats are available in each electoral district. Lok Ral (1998) has given the idea of the democratization and the crisis management of politics in Nepal and shown that political parties encounter difficulties under the SNTV system. This electoral method is utilized in countries such as Afghanistan, Jordan, Vanuatu, and for second chamber elections in Indonesia and Thailand.

Advantages of SNTV:

- Enhances the representation of minority parties and independent candidates.
- Promotes strong party organization, where parties instruct their supporters on how to distribute their votes among candidates.

- Allows several popular non-party candidates to win seats.
- Praised for its simplicity and clarity, making it accessible and understandable for voters.

Disadvantages of SNTV:

- Provides voters with only one vote and offers limited incentives for political parties.
- Results in a significant number of wasted votes.
- Multiple candidacies from the same party can cause internal fragmentation and discord.
- Larger parties may gain a disproportionate number of seats as a bonus.

Proportional Representation

Proportional representation necessitates electoral districts with multiple seats. Werner (1991) has explained about the strengthening of the democracy through the activism of the people and pointed out the right track of utilizing the values of the democratic system as well as norms and values. The fundamental principle behind all PR systems is the deliberate translation of a party's vote share into a corresponding proportion of seats in the legislature. PR systems enable minority parties, regional interests, women, and diverse groups to attain representation. They minimize the likelihood of wasted votes, ensuring that in PR elections with low thresholds, nearly all votes contribute directly to electing preferred candidates.

Three types of PR systems are recognized:

- a) List PR (List Proportional Representation)
- b) MMP (Mixed Member Proportional)
- c) STV (Single Transferable Vote)

These categories include:

- a) List PR, where parties present lists of candidates proportional to their vote share.
- b) MMP, combining single-member districts with additional seats allocated to achieve proportional representation.

c) STV, allowing voters to rank candidates in multi-member districts, ensuring proportional outcomes.

a) List Proportional Representation

In a List Proportional Representation (List PR) system, each party or coalition submits a list of candidates for multi-member electoral districts. Werner (1991) has explained about the strengthening of the democracy through the activism of the people and pointed out the right track of utilizing the values of the democratic system as well as norms and values. Voters cast their ballots for a party, and seats are allocated to parties based on their overall share of the vote. The choice of List PR alone does not fully specify the electoral process; additional details need to be decided. The method used to distribute seats after votes are counted can be either Highest Average (HV) or Largest Remainder Method (LRM). List PR systems can be open, closed, or free list. Countries that use the List PR system include Cambodia, Belgium, South Africa, Netherlands, Israel, Turkey, among others.

Advantages of the List PR system:

- Increases the likelihood of representing minority and cultural groups.
- Promotes the representation of women and disadvantaged communities.
- Ensures that the legislature comprises members from both majority and minority groups.
- Encourages parties to construct balanced lists of candidates.

Disadvantages of the List PR system:

- Weakens the connection between elected legislators and their local constituencies.
- Leads to excessive concentration of power within party headquarters.
- Requires the existence of recognized parties or groups.
- Closed lists prevent voters from directly selecting individual candidates.

b) Mixed Member Proportional System

The Mixed Member Proportional (MMP) system aims to combine the beneficial aspects of Proportional Representation. Under MMP, PR seats are allocated to address any disproportionality arising from district seat results. Voters typically make one choice, contributing to both the total for individual district candidates and their party's overall tally. This hybrid system uses voters' preferences to elect representatives through two distinct methods: List PR and Plurality/Majority. Werner (1991) has explained about the strengthening of the democracy through the activism of the people and pointed out the right track of utilizing the values of the democratic system as well as norms and values. Countries that employ the MMP system include Albania, Germany, Lesotho, Mexico, New Zealand, Venezuela, Italy, among others. In other words, The Mixed Member Proportional (MMP) system seeks to integrate the advantageous features of Proportional Representation. In MMP, proportional seats are allocated to rectify any discrepancies arising from district seat outcomes. Voters generally make a single choice, influencing both the count for local candidates and their party's total tally. This hybrid approach utilizes voter preferences to elect representatives through two separate mechanisms: List PR and Plurality/Majority. Countries employing the MMP system include Albania, Germany, Lesotho, Mexico, New Zealand, Venezuela, and Italy.

Advantages of the MMP system:

- Establishes a connection between elected representatives and their geographic districts.
- Allows voters to cast two votes: one for a political party and another for local representatives.
- Generates two tiers of legislature. This could impact how cohesive groups of elected party representatives operate.

Disadvantages of the MMP system:

- Not as favored as List PR.

- Potential for wasted votes when supporting individual candidates.
- Leads to strategic voting issues.
- Can create conflicts regarding alignment with the National Party's principles.

c) Single Transferable Vote System

The Single Transferable Vote (STV) system is a preferential voting method where voters rank candidates in order of preference. Werner (1991) has explained about the strengthening of the democracy through the activism of the people and pointed out the right track of utilizing the values of the democratic system as well as norms and values. Candidates who reach or exceed a specified quota of first preference votes are elected in the initial count. In subsequent counts, surplus votes from elected candidates are redistributed based on voters' subsequent preferences. This system is utilized in countries such as the Republic of Ireland, Malta, Estonia, Australia, British Columbia, and local elections in Scotland.

Advantages of the STV system:

- Provides voters with the option to choose both between parties and among candidates within parties.
- Results in final outcomes that maintain a reasonable level of fairness and proportionality.
- Offers a greater opportunity for popular independent candidates to be elected compared to List PR.
- Allows voters to impact the formation of post-election coalitions.

The demerits of STV system:

- It may not be suitable for societies with low levels of literacy and numeracy.
- It can lead to internal fragmentation within political parties.
- The complexities of counting votes in an STV system are considerable.
- In practice, it can prove to be somewhat challenging.

- In addition to these electoral systems, there are also various other systems in use, listed below.

Limited Vote System (LV)

The Limited Vote System is an electoral method focused on candidates, used in multi-member districts where voters possess more than one vote but fewer votes than the number of candidates to be elected. The candidate with the highest number of votes wins a seat.

Cumulative Vote System (CV)

In this electoral system, which operates in multi-member constituencies, voters have the freedom to distribute their votes among multiple candidates as they see fit. A key feature of this system is that voters can choose to spread their votes across several candidates or focus all their votes on a single candidate.

Finding

The description provides a comprehensive overview of electoral systems and their relevance for any country based on its geographical, social, economic, and cultural characteristics. Nepal is a country characterized by multiculturalism, Multireligiosity, multilingualism, and diverse ethnic groups. These groups often experience overlapping social divisions. Each group has distinct cultures, customs, traditions, and languages, contributing to unique lifestyles. Werner (1991) has explained about the strengthening of the democracy through the activism of the people and pointed out the right track of utilizing the values of the democratic system as well as norms and values. Many of these ethnic and caste groups face socio-economic marginalization, lacking constitutional rights and access to essential services like healthcare and education. Consequently, their representation in various fields, including politics, is limited. However, in recent years, there has been a noticeable change as people have become more capable of determining their representation, particularly in political spheres.

Nepal has a lengthy history of using the First-Past-the-Post (FPTP) system for legislative

elections and Single Transferable Vote (STV) for assembly elections. However, the Constituent Assembly election of 2008 introduced a Parallel Mixed system that included Proportional Representation (PR) alongside FPTP (Mishra, 2008, 9). This election marked a significant milestone by providing diverse groups with the opportunity to be represented in the constituent assembly. Notably, the representation of women reached approximately 33% (32.78%) in the CA 1, a historic achievement in Nepal's electoral history. The CA Election Act of 2008 mandated the creation of closed lists under the PR system, specifying quotas for various groups such as Madhesis (31.2%), Dalits (13%), Adibasi Janajatis (37.8%), backward areas (4%), and others (30.2%), with a requirement for women's representation at 50% (Dahal, 2009, 23).

Despite these provisions, some indigenous Janajati groups like Sunuwar, Meche, Dhanuk, Dolpo, Baram, Balunge, Pahari, and Tokpegola were not selected from the closed lists. Conversely, Janajati groups that did not field candidates, such as Kusunda, Bankaria, Raute, Sural, Hayu, Raji, Koosbadia, Singmama, Thudam, Bote, Bhote, Darai, Tajpuriya, Chhantyal, Fri, Larke, Lepcha, Chayrotan, Tingaule, Thakali, and Kishan, did not participate in the election process (Upreti, 2009, 7 / Election Commission Report 2064). The Constituent Assembly (CA) election aimed to achieve inclusivity by ensuring representation for indigenous groups, Janajatis, Madhesis, women, Dalits, the handicapped, and the third gender. Despite these efforts, certain groups did not achieve representation in the first CA.

The two dominant political parties, Nepali Congress (NC) and CPN-UML, held similar perspectives regarding mixed elections. In contrast, smaller political entities like Madhesi Janadhikar Forum Nepal, Terai Madhesi Loktantrik, Janamorcha Nepal, RPP, RPP Nepal, and Nepal Dalit Janajati favored the PR system, while others preferred the FPTP system. Therefore, the adoption of the parallel mixed system (combining FPTP and PR) was seen as a more inclusive approach. It aimed to enhance the participation of marginalized and underrepresented groups such as Adibasi,

Janajati, Madhesi, women, Dalit, handicapped, and third gender individuals, aligning with their demographic proportions in society.

In the Constituent Assembly (CA) election for 601 seats, 240 members were elected through the First-Past-the-Post (FPTP) system, 335 members were elected through Proportional Representation (PR), and 26 members were nominated by the government. A total of 25 parties secured representation in CA 1. Some parties did not win any seats through FPTP but gained representation through the PR system. Despite achieving significant inclusiveness compared to the past, the proportional aspect was not fully realized.

In countries practicing the Parallel Mixed System, it is typically expected that seats allocated through FPTP and PR are balanced. However, in Nepal, this balance was not maintained. The presence of two ballot papers confused illiterate voters, resulting in a 5% invalid vote rate, the highest recorded to date. Werner (1991) has explained about the strengthening of the democracy through the activism of the people and pointed out the right track of utilizing the values of the democratic system as well as norms and values. This suggests that different electoral systems might have produced different outcomes.

Therefore, there is a pressing need for extensive national discussion and debate to address the challenges posed by the Parallel Mixed System and to explore potential improvements. (Upreti, 2009, 13).

Conclusion and Recommendation

Nepal urgently requires a reformed electoral system that improves upon the existing Parallel Mixed system. Future elections must be meticulously planned to enhance voter engagement and foster a sense of ownership and participation in the nation-building process, particularly in institutionalizing federalism. The electoral framework should allow for corrections of past mistakes observed in the Constituent Assembly (CA) elections, where voters

expressed dissatisfaction with the closed list of the PR system.

In the List PR system, voters were unaware of the candidates they were supporting under the party list, where party leaders exerted significant influence over candidate selection, sidelining the authority of the election commission. The flaws of the Parallel Mixed system have already been acknowledged, necessitating a proactive approach to address and rectify these issues. It is crucial to learn from these experiences and adopt a more suitable electoral system that meets the specific needs of Nepal.

Several practical recommendations can be proposed to policymakers aimed at addressing the current anomalies and challenges within Nepal's electoral systems. These measures aim to enhance the effectiveness and fairness of both the Parallel Mixed system and other electoral mechanisms:

Enhanced Voter Education: Implement comprehensive voter education programs to increase awareness among voters about different electoral systems, their implications, and how to effectively participate in elections.

Transparent Candidate Selection: Ensure transparency in the selection of candidates under the List PR system by limiting party leader influence and empowering election commissions to oversee and validate candidate nominations.

Balanced Representation: Strive for balanced representation between FPTP and PR seats to ensure equitable distribution of seats among various political parties and marginalized groups.

Inclusive Electoral Participation: Promote inclusive electoral participation by addressing barriers faced by marginalized groups such as women, Dalits, Janajatis, Madhesis, the disabled, and the third gender. This could include special provisions or quotas to encourage their meaningful participation.

Electoral Reform Dialogue: Foster a national dialogue on electoral reforms to solicit diverse perspectives and consensus-building among political parties, civil society organizations, and the public. This dialogue should explore potential improvements to the electoral system

that align with Nepal's socio-political context and aspirations for democratic governance.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Establish robust mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the electoral process to identify and rectify shortcomings promptly. This could involve independent oversight bodies and regular reviews of electoral laws and practices.

Technological Integration: Integrate appropriate technology to streamline voter registration, improve ballot counting accuracy, and enhance overall transparency and efficiency in the electoral process.

By implementing these practical measures, policymakers can address existing challenges and improve the integrity and inclusivity of electoral systems in Nepal, ensuring they better reflect the will and aspirations of the Nepali people.

Several strategic recommendations can be put forth to policymakers aiming to address current challenges and anomalies within Nepal's electoral systems:

Equal Seat Allocation: It is recommended to allocate an equal percentage of seats for both First-Past-the-Post (FPTP) and Proportional Representation (PR) systems to ensure a balanced representation across different electoral methodologies.

Enhanced Voter Awareness Programs: Conduct specialized voter awareness campaigns to educate the electorate about various electoral processes, enhancing their understanding and participation in elections.

Practical Election Training: Implement practical training sessions for election stakeholders to minimize the incidence of invalid votes and ensure smooth electoral operations.

Empowerment of Election Commission: Grant full authority to the Election Commission over candidate selection in the List PR system to enhance transparency and fairness in the electoral process.

Consideration of STV System: Consider adopting the Single Transferable Vote (STV) system for closed list elections to provide voters

with more direct influence over candidate selection.

Implementation of Thresholds: Introduce a minimal threshold, such as 5% of the national vote, akin to systems in Germany, Russia, or New Zealand. This threshold would prevent parties failing to meet this mark from gaining seats through the PR List, promoting political consolidation and reducing fragmentation.

Promotion of Party Cohesion: The implementation of a threshold system can also encourage smaller or weaker parties to consolidate their efforts, fostering greater political coherence and stability.

By implementing these comprehensive measures, policymakers can potentially enhance the integrity, inclusivity, and effectiveness of Nepal's electoral systems, ensuring they better serve the interests and aspirations of the nation's diverse populace.

References

- Baral, L. (2009). Local leadership and governance in Nepal: Lecture and handout, Dhulikhel, organized by NCCS.
- Baral, L. R., & Rose, L. E. (1998). Democratization and crisis of governance in Nepal. In S. K. Mitra & D. Rothermund (Eds.), *Legitimacy and conflict in South Asia* (pp. xx-xx). New Delhi: Manohar Publishers.
- Cooper, R. (1999). Integration and disintegration. *Journal of Democracy*, 10(1), 34-47.
- Dahal, R. K. (2009). Elections, electoral system, and inclusive democracy in Nepal: Lecture and handout, Dhulikhel, organized by NCCS.
- Dahal, D. R. (1997). Challenge to good governance in Nepal. A report submitted to the International Institute for Electoral and Democratic Assistance, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Election Commission Report. (2008). *Sambhidhansabha 2064: Eke Jhalak*. Kathmandu: Election Commission.
- Kumar, S. (2000). *Election and electoral system*. New Delhi: Institute of Constitutional and Parliamentary Studies.
- Mishra, B. P. (2008). *Nirvachan pranali: Bigatka anubbutiharu ra bhavishyako ganatanya*. Kathmandu.
- Mishra, B. P. (1999, June 29). Elections '99: Yet another milestone. *The Kathmandu Post*.
- NESAC. (1998). *Nepal: Human Development Report 1998*. Kathmandu: Nepal South Asian Center.
- Nohlen, D. (1996). *Elections and electoral systems*. New Delhi: Macmillan India Ltd.
- Peters, W. (1991). *Society on the run*. New York: M. E. Sharpe.
- Reynolds, A., Reilly, B., & Ellis, A. (2005). *Electoral system design: The new international IDEA handbook*. Stockholm: International IDEA.
- Shah, B. P. (1998, November 12). Nirbachan pranali ra loktantrako sudridhikaran (Electoral system and the consolidation of democracy). Paper presented at the Seminar on Politics of Consensus and Implementation of Constitution, Kathmandu.
- Upreti, N. (2009). Electoral system and inclusion: Lecture and handout, Dhulikhel, organized by NCCS.